

EFFECTIVE USE OF INNOVATIVE EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING PRACTICAL CLASSES OF THE SUBJECT "LATIN LANGUAGE AND MEDICAL TERMINOLOGY"

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Abstracts: this article will consider innovative technologies for training students, which will give the most accurate effect and coefficient of mastering new material by students, as well as form professional skills. This article describes modern innovative technologies that have manifested themselves in pedagogical practice, including in my professional activities. It is possible to expand the range of teaching methods used using innovative technologies.

Key words: innovative technologies, knowledge and skills, critical thinking, cooperation pedagogy, professional activity.

The use of innovative methods of teaching in practical classes of the Latin language. "Not knowing - not scary, but scary - not learning". Chinese wisdom.

I. Introduction. Currently, changes are taking place in the educational system of the Independent Republic of Uzbekistan, which leads to the need to develop competency systems based on competencies. There are many examples of innovative technologies for teaching students in the pedagogical literature, but in my opinion, not all of them can be used in practical classes in Latin. In the modern conditions of modernization of education, the goals and objectives facing the teacher are being changed. Emphasis is shifted from "knowledge acquisition" to "skill formation". Innovative pedagogical technologies are being introduced that ensure the accounting and development of individual characteristics of students. Modern educational technologies can be considered the main condition for improving the quality of education, reducing the burden on students and making the most of the study time.

Speaking about the use of innovative teaching methods, attention should be paid to the development of critical thinking of students and the organization of independent work in practical classes in Latin. I mean a set of methods, techniques and tools that not only increase the quality of education, but also help to form professional and general cultural competencies of medical students. Critical thinking as creative, analytical thinking helps students solve the following tasks in learning: - setting priorities; - acceptance of personal responsibility; - increase the level of work with information. The independent work of students is inextricably linked with the development of critical thinking. The organization of independent work of students involves the participation of the teacher in the planning of the lesson and the assessment of the results. The problem with teaching and learning Latin is that it has evolved from the languages of science, culture, jurisprudence and religion into the pure professional language of medical workers. This reduced his opportunities for development and teaching, and also reduced his interest in learning this remarkable and rich language. For this reason, I believe that the use of innovative methods of teaching in practical classes on the subject of "Latin and medical terminology" will improve the teaching and perception of medical students.

It should be noted that Latin is the basis of modern languages such as French, Portuguese, Spanish, Italian, Romanian, Moldovan, Catalan, retro-roman, Provençal. Also, knowledge of Latin makes it easier for students to learn these languages.

II. Examples of the Latin language on the use of innovative technologies in practical training. To improve the quality of education, it is necessary and necessary to use active innovative educational technologies that allow students to convey the necessary knowledge and

skills. Innovative methods cannot completely replace traditional methods, but my experience shows that they increase students' interest in learning, as well as expand the amount of data they remember. There are several groups of innovative teaching methods. These include: - problem education; - technology for the development of "critical thinking"; -ICT; - design methods in teaching; - technology of using game methods in teaching; - collaborative training (collective and Universal work).

Problematic teaching method. This method helps to develop creative thinking to the maximum, teaches students to think about the essence of phenomena and look for a relationship between them. Problem Education requires students to have certain intellectual abilities, thinking actions, forcing them to fight difficulties. The basis of problem education is a system of ready-made knowledge and skills obtained both in practical classes in Latin and independently. In order to successfully use problem education, you need to clearly understand the requirements for this teaching method: - the problem must be expressed clearly and clearly; - the problem must have a certain complexity; - the problem should be interesting for students; - there must be enough training materials to find a solution to the problem. From my practice, I can give examples of such training. For example: I give students a task on the topic: "recipe" with mistakes made in advance. Task: to find and correct errors, analyze answers.

Method of technology for the development of "critical thinking". The purpose of developing "critical thinking" is to form a culture of reading and encourage independent creative activity. The constructive basis of the" technology of critical thinking "is the main model of three stages of the organization of the educational process:"challenge-feedback". At the "call" stage, existing knowledge and ideas on the topic under study are called and updated from memory. The situation of difficulty is skillfully created by the teacher with a question. At the stage of "understanding", acquaintance with new information and its systematization are carried out. Students will have the opportunity to understand the information received, as well as the opportunity to formulate questions when old and new information are interconnected. In the thinking phase, students consolidate new knowledge and incorporate them into new concepts. Students' methods of "opposing thinking" include the following methods:

"Ask questions" method. The teacher asks a question, offers to consider and discuss the answer. The question should be such that the answer involves reflection and analysis. Frequently asking questions becomes a debate, where students learn to ask questions themselves and formulate them correctly. I use this technique in practical training in the "morphology" section. Methods of" critical thinking "include" 'mental attack", "cluster", etc. "Mental attack" is one of the most popular ways to stimulate creative activity, allowing you to find solutions to complex problems by applying special discussion rules. It is widely used in audiences to find unconventional solutions to various tasks. The mental attack method was developed by Alex Osborne in 1953. The method is based on the assumption that one of the main obstacles to the emergence of new ideas is "fear of evaluation": students often do not speak out loud, fearing skepticism from the teacher and other students. The purpose of the application of mental attack is to exclude the evaluation component during the practical training of the Latin language. The classic mental attack technique proposed by Osborn is based on two basic principles: - "delay judgment"; - "quality is born from quantity".

This approach involves applying several rules. Criticism of any mistakes of students during classes is excluded. Students who work in interactive groups must make sure they are evaluated on their work. There should be many questions: each student is given the opportunity to ask the

maximum number of questions and answer them. At the final stage, the best answers are selected. In recent years, “electronic brainstorming” (online brainstorming) using Internet technologies has become widespread. This allows you to eliminate the “fear of evaluation”, since it provides anonymity, allows you to solve a number of problems of a traditional brain attack.

Information and communication technology method. The implementation of this method can be defined as technologies used to access, collect, manipulate, present or report data. ICT (henceforth referred to as ICT in the text) includes both technical tools and software. The main tool of ICT for the information environment of any educational system is the capabilities of a personal computer and software installed on it. Currently, there are many opinions on whether to use a computer when teaching Latin. Some believe that a computer can replace a teacher, others believe that a computer cannot provide material because the teacher does so. In my opinion, the computer serves only as a learning tool. It should be remembered that the computer has many advantages: it combines video-audio data, text data, and the computer also offers great opportunities for testing the level of knowledge of Latin or the subject with the participation of a teacher, which reduces the time of checking the results. The tests can be very diverse: Joker characters, selected, template. I use tests in practical training:

- using multiple choices (with one or more correct answer options);
- with passes (with different capabilities to support the user);
- linguistic games (crosswords).

So, for example, the electronic version of the test allows students to place objects inside the document in the necessary places, delete them, group them, in accordance with the task, enter the necessary items and like etc. Thus, the use of a computer for a teacher provides the opportunity to constantly improve educational materials, as well as introduce new organizational forms of teaching. There are other types of act. For example, TV, but we do not have centralized TV capabilities. In the practical training of the Latin language, the main method of ICT is presentations. They differ in the types of speech activity (in reading, writing, learning to speak), aspects of speech (in teaching vocabulary, grammar or phonetics), types of support (meaningful, semantic and illustrative). I use presentations that facilitate the use of different language and speech exercises in the practical classes of Latin. Presentations allow students to reveal their creative abilities thanks to the computer, the introduction of ICT - significantly diversified the process of perception and development of information, and then analysis and sorting are possible.

III. The technology of using game methods in teaching. This is perhaps the most favorite method of students among the innovative technologies that we use in practical classes in Latin. It is worth paying attention and focusing in detail on examples of phonetic, lexical and grammatical games in practical classes. The consolidation of phonetics is promoted by:

a) a puzzle game. The student pronounces words in which the same sound occurs, and the other students must guess it and write it on the blackboard. For example:

- arteria (arteria) – artery,
- dens (dens) – tooth,
- nomen (nomen) – name, title,
- medicina (medicine) – medicine.

b) the game is a competition. I write diphthongs (double-voiced) on the blackboard. There are four of them: ae, oe, au, eu. I give students a task - to write as many words with diphthongs as possible, pronounce them, paying attention to the stress and pronunciation of sounds. For example:

-diphthongs –ae-, -oe- – are pronounced as one sound. –ae- pronounced as the Uzbek or English "e".

Student "A" - writes words with diphthongs –ae- on the blackboard, pronounced as Uzbek or English "e". Example: gangraena (gangrene) – necrosis, aeger (eger) – patient, praeparatum (preparatum) drug.

Student "B" -writes words with diphthongs –oe-, which are pronounced as the Uzbek or English "e". Example: Foeniculum - fennel, drugstore dill, Synoestrolum - synestrol. Uzbek or English diphthong –au- pronounced as a Uzbek or English "av" (monosyllabic) Student "B" -writes words with a diphthong –au-, pronounced as a Uzbek or English "av". Example: Aurum (avrum) – gold, Daunomycinum (davnomycinum) – daunomycin. Uzbek or English diphthong –eu-, pronounced as Uzbek or English ev (monosyllabic) Student "C" -writes words with diphthong –eu-, pronounced as Uzbek or English "ev" (monosyllabic). Example: Eucalyptus (evkalyptus) – eucalyptus, Eucommia (evkommia) – eucommia

c) imitation game. Students try to repeat tongue twisters or proverbs. The winner is the one who repeats the tongue twister or proverb the fastest. For example: Ego eo cum ego eo; Paulus Paulam amat, sed Paula alium amat; Bella femina habet femina bella.

d) lexical games - aimed at working out new terminologies, mastering the mechanisms of word formations, phraseological units. And I offer such tasks to students during practical classes in Latin:

1) "Color pictures". Students form small groups of three or four people, each group is given a task, they receive two sets of colored cards. On the blue cards – phrases in Uzbek or English; on the red cards – their equivalent in Latin. The team that made these pictures the fastest wins.

2) "Fight in the ring". Students work in pairs under the supervision of a judge. Each of them prepares a written list of terms in Uzbek or English and also their equivalent in Latin. Student "A" reads out the terms written down by him to student "B" in Uzbek or English, student "B" within three to five seconds must name these terms and give an explanation in Latin. This happens alternately.

3) "Snow avalanche". I give the students a task: to identify the known term elements, explain their meaning, write the terms in Uzbek or English transcription. For example: dystrophia Student "A" identifies a well-known term element -trophia (Greek. trophe). Student "B" explains its meaning (nutrition). Student "C" gives a translation of the term – eating disorder. For example: stomatologia. Student "A" identifies the well-known term element stomat- (Greek stoma) Student "B" explains its meaning (hole, mouth). Student "C" gives a translation – teaching about diseases of the oral cavity.

4) "Lotto". Each student receives a lotto card with a medical term written in Latin on the topic. I give an explanation of a term, and the student must find its equivalent in the card.

5) "Ping Pong". Students work in pairs and very quickly. Student "A" calls the word-forming element in Latin or Greek. Student "B" gives the appropriate translation in Russian and gives an example of a medical term based on this word-forming element. The roles change in turn. Student "A": angi(o) – (Greek, angeion) -> Student "B" – vessel , angiography. Student "B" somat – (Greek soma) Student "A" – body, somatoscopy. Lexical games can also include: riddles, puzzles, crosswords. But the biggest opportunities for the development of cognitive activity of students are professional games related to the future profession of a physician, where students play the role of: nurse-patient, doctor-patient, doctor-nurse. Collaborative learning method (team and group work) This method is not yet widespread enough in pedagogical practice, due to certain

professional and psychological difficulties, both on the part of the teacher and on the part of students. Group work of students stimulates close communication of students with each other, which leads to the formation of social behavior skills, the assimilation of collaboration technologies. A distinctive feature of a teacher who uses this method is that he speaks little, but listens and observes a lot. The introduction of this method of teaching "in cooperation" team and group work in the educational process is important for both the teacher and the student. It is important for a teacher to discover the hidden talents and abilities of his students. As my practice suggests, students are grouped into groups of five or six people and each group should have a well-prepared student. Everyone is given one task, while the role of each is specified. Each student is responsible not only for the result of his work, but also for the result of the whole group, so weak students try to find out from the strong what they do not understand, and strong students strive for the weak to figure out the task. And the whole group benefits from this, because by joint efforts gaps in knowledge are eliminated. The task should not be large in volume, but clearly formulated. Students should be given some time to lapping up inside the group. My task is to monitor the work of the groups and provide advice if necessary. And also, not to pay attention to the noise that arises in the process of work and to settle emerging conflicts, if necessary, as practice shows – students perceive this method with great interest and it helps to reveal their creative abilities. I have tested several more methods of innovative teaching, both at the level of a group of students and at the intergroup level. First of all, these are: "Brain-ring", "Entertaining quiz". For the quiz, I selected topics: "Entertaining anatomy using term elements", "Winged Latin expressions". "Brain ring". The group is divided into two teams or each group becomes a participant in the competition. On the "Brain ring" I offer such contests: 1. black box; 2. add a phrase; 3. questions in envelopes; 4. finish or fill in, etc. Students are happy to take part in the "Brain Ring" and "Quiz".

IV. Conclusions:

1. The use of innovative technology methods allows you to expand the capabilities of the teacher, as well as increase interest in the subject being studied by students.
2. The use of innovative methods does not replace the old classical methods of teaching the subject, but only complements and expands this process.
3. Innovative methods make it possible to create conditions for a more complete disclosure of students' capabilities.
4. Such innovative methods as the project method, group work, identify weaknesses and gaps in students' knowledge in time, which allows the teacher to analyze it and focus on these gaps.
5. Innovative methods contribute to the expansion of methodological knowledge and skills of the teacher, as well as to the disclosure of his organizational abilities.
6. Independent work, as one of the innovative methods, fruitfully affects the quality of students' knowledge, as well as their ability to expand their skills and abilities to work with literature and the possibilities of ICT.

It can be concluded that information technologies will continue to improve, new technologies and new ICT capabilities will appear, which will require the teacher to constantly be in the mainstream of pedagogical science.

Literatures

1. Maxmudov, Z., Sharipov, B., & Bo'riyev, D. (2023). Tibbiyot universitetlarida lotin tili va tibbiy terminologiya fanini o'qitishning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari. *Science and innovation in the education system*, 2(1), 5-10.

2. Mardanovich, M. Z., Aliaskarovna, S. U., Kenjaevna, B. M., Genjebaevna, A. P., & Salimovich, S. B. (2021). Some Considerations about Legal Solutions and Practices of Certain Problems Writing Recipes. *Annals of the Romanian Society for Cell Biology*, 5341-5352.

3. ZAFAR, M., BOBUR, S., & DILMUROD, B. R. (2021). Scientific and pedagogical basis of teaching the theory of decisions in school chemistry. *International Journal of Philosophical Studies and Social Sciences*, 1(3), 192-196.

4. Maxmudov, Z. M., & Sharipov, B. S. (2021). LOTIN TILI VA TIBBIY TERMINOLOGIYA FANINI O'QITISHDA INNOVATSION TEXNOLOGIYALARDAN FOYDALANISHNING DIDAKTIK TAMOYILLARI VA UNING ASOSI HAQIDA FIKRLAR. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 2(6), 1028-1033.

5. Sharipov, B., Makhmudov, Z., & Buriyev, D. (2023). The role of teaching latin in the course of subject training of future foreign language teachers. *Science and innovation in the education system*, 2(1), 11-14.

6. Mardanovich, M. Z., Salimovich, S. B., & Arzimurodovich, B. D. (2021). Modern Methods of Teaching Latin and Medical Terminology in Uzbekistan. *International Journal of Development and Public Policy*, 1(5), 190-192.

7. Sharipov, B., Makhmudov, Z., & Buriyev, D. (2023). Features of teaching latin to students medical universities studying in english. *Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences*, 2(1), 21-25.

8. Sharipov, B., Makhmudov, Z., & Buriyev, D. (2023). Influence of the latin language on the formation of medical terminology. *Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences*, 2(1), 16-20.

9. Maxmudov, Z. M. Lotin tili va tibbiyot terminologiyasi fanini o'qitishda zamonaviy pedagogik texnologiyalardan unumli foydalanish istiqbollari. *Urganch davlat universiteti, "Ilm sarchashmalari*, 118-120.

10. Mardanovich, M. Z., Salimoviche, S. B., & Arzimurodoviche, B. D. (2021). Reviews of effective use of educational methods in teaching latin and medical terminology. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 11(4), 381-386.

11. Maxmudov, Z. M. Retsept yozishda duch kelinadigan ayrim muammolarning qonuniy yechimi va amalda qo'llash haqida ba'zi mulohazalar, "O'zbekistonda ilmiy-amaliy tadqiqotlar" mavzusidagi.

12. Maxmudov, Z. M. (2022). Teaching correct pronunciation of latin as an international language of medicine in medical education institutions, Global Technovation 5th International Multidisciplinary Scientific Conference Hosted From Paris, France. *March 30th*, 30-31.

13. Mardanovich, M. Z., & Salimovich, S. B. Auditoriyadan tashqari ta'lim-tarbiyaga *Ташкентского государственного стоматологического института по адресу: Республика Узбекистан, 100047, г. Ташкент, ул. Махтумкули, 103. Цель конференции—знакомство и обмен опытом в обучении и в работе с цифровыми данными, технологиями их применения в гуманитарных* (p. 455).

14. Omonova, M., & Makhmudov, Z. (2023). Modern signs of using the quince plant in folk medicine. *International Bulletin of Medical Sciences and Clinical Research*, 3(4), 41-45.

15. Qurbonova, Z., & Maxmudov, Z. (2023). LOTIN TILIDA KLINIK TERMINLARNING TO'G'RI QO'LLANISH YUZASIDAN FIKRLAR. *Евразийский журнал академических исследований*, 3(3 Part 3), 23-27.

16. Махмудов, З. М., & Шарипов, Б. С. Талабаларнинг фанни яхши ўрганишлари учун психо-эмоционал таъсир этишда халқ мақол ва маталларидан тўғри фойдаланиш (лотин тили ва тиббий терминология фани мисолида). *Zbiór artykułów naukowych recenzowanych*, 112.

17. Maxmudov, Z. M. (2022). Lotin tili va tibbiy terminologiyani o'rganishda o'zbek tili grammatikasining o'rni. *Science and Education*, 3(11), 756-759.

18. Mardanovich, M. Z. (2022). The place of problematic and heuristic methods in the process of teaching latin and medical terminology.

19. Mardanovich, M. Z., Salimovich, S. B., & Arzimurodovich, B. D. (2021). Developing Students Attitudes Towards the Environment When Teaching a Foreign Languages. *Texas Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies*, 1(1), 199-201.

20. Maxmudov, Z. (2022). RETSEPTURADA ERITMALARNING QO'LLANILISHI YUZASIDAN AYRIM MULOHAZALAR. *Евразийский журнал академических исследований*, 2(6), 524-527.

21. Makhmudov Zafar Mardanovich, Tuychiyev son of Nadir Khudoyberdi, Usmanov is the son of Sardar Fame. (2023). SOME OF THE MOST USED FORMS OF MEDICINE IN MEDICAL PRACTICE - THE USE OF TABLETS AND SOLUTIONS. THEORETICAL ASPECTS IN THE FORMATION OF PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES, 2(13), 20-26. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8008614>

22. Maxmudov Zafar Mardanovich, & Normurodova Sohiba Mallaevna. (2023). LOTIN TILINING ZAMONAVIY TILLARGA BEVOSITA VA BILVOSITA TA'SIRI. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8034739>

23. Makhmudov Zafar Mardanovich, Tuychiyev son of Nadir Khudoyberdi, Usmanov is the son of Sardar Fame. (2023). SOME OF THE MOST USED FORMS OF MEDICINE IN MEDICAL PRACTICE - THE USE OF TABLETS AND SOLUTIONS. THEORETICAL ASPECTS IN THE FORMATION OF PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES, 2(13), 20-26. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8008614>